

**Nexus between Financial Sector Development and Environmental Degradation:
Evidence from Selected Sub-Saharan African Economies**

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Abstract

This study investigates the nexus between financial sector development and environmental degradation in selected Sub-Saharan African (SSA) economies, with a specific focus on capital market indicators—market capitalization-to-GDP and stock market turnover ratio. Using panel data from seven purposively selected SSA countries (Côte d’Ivoire, Ghana, Kenya, Mauritius, Namibia, Nigeria, and South Africa) over the period 1995–2023, the study adopts a longitudinal panel design and employs the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (P-ARDL) model to estimate both short-run and long-run dynamics. Environmental degradation is measured using two key indicators: carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and ecological footprint (disaggregated into per capita and index measures), while controlling for variables such as energy consumption, urbanization, FDI, and secondary school enrolment. The findings reveal that in the short run, capital market indicators have weak or delayed effects on environmental degradation, with only lagged stock market turnover significantly reducing CO₂ emissions. However, in the long run, market capitalization significantly lowers CO₂ emissions and ecological footprint per capita, but paradoxically increases the ecological footprint index, suggesting persistent pressures on natural biocapacity. Stock market turnover is positively associated with CO₂ emissions but negatively related to both ecological footprint measures, reflecting its dual role in promoting economic activity and facilitating green investment. Granger causality tests confirm unidirectional causality from capital market development to ecological footprint but no significant causality with CO₂ emissions. Based on these results, the study recommends strengthening environmental regulatory frameworks within capital markets, promoting ESG-compliant financial instruments, and improving financial infrastructure and literacy to facilitate a transition toward environmentally sustainable investment in SSA.

Keywords: *Environmental degradation, Environmental Kuzznet Curve, market capitalisation to GDP, stock market turnover ratio,*

1. Introduction

The pursuit of economic growth and environmental sustainability represents one of the most complex challenges of the 21st century. Climate change, driven by the increased concentration of greenhouse gases (GHGs), particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), has emerged as a significant global concern with profound implications for development policy, public health, and ecological balance. Among the various GHGs, CO₂ is the most dominant, contributing over 60% to the global greenhouse effect (Acaravci & Ozturk, 2010). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), global CO₂ emissions have been rising rapidly since the 1970s, mainly due to the intensification of industrial activity, energy consumption, and urbanization (IPCC, 2014). This trend has heightened the tension between economic development and environmental preservation, particularly in developing regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where economic aspirations are growing amid increasing environmental vulnerability (Olubusoye & Dasuki, 2020).

In response to these dynamics, attention has turned to the role of the financial sector in shaping environmental outcomes. Financial markets, including banking institutions and capital markets facilitate investment, consumption, and production, all of which are inherently linked to environmental quality. As financial systems expand and deepen, they influence the allocation of resources, including investments in environmentally friendly technologies or, conversely, in carbon-intensive industries. The nature and direction of this influence remains a subject of intense empirical debate. On one hand, financial development is posited to improve environmental quality by facilitating green investments, supporting innovation in clean technologies, and encouraging energy-efficient infrastructure through mechanisms such as green bonds, environmental risk assessments, and sustainability-linked credit (Tamazian, Chousa, & Vadlamannati, 2009; Shahbaz, Khan, & Tahir, 2013). On the other hand, increased financial activity can drive greater consumption and industrial expansion, thereby accelerating environmental degradation through higher emissions and resource depletion (Mahalik & Mallick, 2014; Chang, 2015).

In the SSA context, financial systems have traditionally been underdeveloped, but recent decades have witnessed significant reforms aimed at deepening financial markets. Among key indicators of financial development are market capitalization to gross domestic product (GDP) and stock market turnover ratio, which reflect the size and efficiency of the capital markets. These indicators capture how well financial institutions mobilize savings and allocate capital, and are therefore critical in understanding the environmental consequences of financial market expansion. However, existing empirical research in SSA has largely focused on banking sector indicators such as credit to the private sector and broad money supply, while the environmental implications of capital market development remain underexplored (Hamdan, Azman-Saini, & Rasid, 2018; Lestari, Fitriani, & Permata, 2020).

Moreover, the empirical literature examining the relationship between financial development and environmental degradation is inconclusive. While some studies have reported that financial development improves environmental quality by promoting eco-friendly technologies (Sadorsky, 2011; Shahbaz et al., 2013), others have shown a positive correlation between financial development and CO₂ emissions, particularly in countries with weak environmental regulations (Al-Mulali, Saboori, & Ozturk, 2015; Le, Le, & Taghizadeh-Hesary, 2020). These mixed results suggest the presence of contextual heterogeneity and methodological differences, particularly with respect to the selection of financial indicators, environmental proxies, and estimation techniques.

A notable shortcoming in many existing studies is the reliance on CO₂ emissions as the sole indicator of environmental degradation. Although CO₂ emissions are a major contributor to global warming, they do not capture the broader ecological impacts of economic activity. Ecological footprint, which includes a range of environmental stressors such as land use, water consumption, and waste assimilation, provides a more comprehensive measure of environmental pressure (Al-Mulali et al., 2015). Employing both CO₂ emissions and ecological footprint as environmental indicators enables a more robust assessment of the environmental effects of financial development and economic growth. This study adopts this dual-measurement approach to provide a holistic understanding of environmental degradation in SSA.

In addition to improving the choice of environmental indicators, this study addresses methodological limitations in previous research. Many studies have utilized static panel data methods such as fixed or random effects models, which may lead to biased estimates due to parameter heterogeneity across countries. The application of advanced dynamic panel estimators such as the Mean Group (MG) and Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimators developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (1999) allows for heterogeneity in short-run dynamics while imposing long-run homogeneity. These estimators are particularly suitable for analyzing panel data with varying degrees of economic development and financial structure, as is the case in SSA.

Furthermore, while many studies have examined the individual effects of financial development or economic growth on environmental quality, few have explored their joint impact, particularly in SSA. Some exceptions include the works of Tamazian et al. (2009), Kwakwa, Alhassan, and Aboagye (2018) and Aljadani, A. (2022), but these remain limited in scope and do not incorporate capital market indicators. Given the growing relevance of financial markets in the development strategies of SSA countries, investigating the joint influence of market capitalization and stock market turnover on environmental degradation becomes essential. This study contributes to the literature by filling this empirical gap, offering insights into how capital market development interacts with economic growth to influence environmental outcomes.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptualizing Environmental Degradation

Environmental degradation is a multifaceted global challenge that encompasses the deterioration of environmental quality and the depletion of natural resources such as air, water, and soil. This deterioration manifests through biodiversity loss, deforestation, desertification, rising sea levels, and increasing greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations (Brown et al., 1987; Tian et al., 2004). Environmental degradation results from both natural processes and human activities, with the latter playing a dominant role in recent decades (Malcolm & Pitelka, 2000; Johnson et al., 1997; Maurya et al., 2020). Key drivers include rapid industrialization, population growth, urban expansion, and unsustainable consumption of natural resources (Chopra, 2016; Astri, 1993). According to Conserve Energy Future (2020), environmental degradation is broadly defined as any disturbance or alteration in the natural environment perceived to be harmful or undesirable.

A central component of environmental degradation is the emission of greenhouse gases, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is the most dominant GHG released by human activities (IPCC, 2018). The combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial activities are primary contributors to increased atmospheric CO₂ levels, which in turn enhance the

greenhouse effect and result in global warming (Gasser & Luderer, 2018). While CO₂ is a non-toxic and naturally occurring gas, its excessive concentration due to anthropogenic activities has made it the leading contributor to climate change, responsible for over 60 percent of global warming effects (Acaravci & Ozturk, 2010). The rise in global temperatures, more frequent climate anomalies, and environmental disasters are direct consequences of increased GHG emissions (IPCC, 2014; Olubusoye & Dasuki, 2020).

2.2 Indicators of Environmental Degradation

The measurement of environmental degradation has evolved to include both direct and composite indicators. In this study, environmental degradation is assessed using two principal indicators: carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and ecological footprint.

Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions

Carbon dioxide emissions refer to the release of CO₂ into the atmosphere, primarily from burning fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and natural gas, as well as from cement production and deforestation (World Bank, 2018; Eurostat, 2017). As a greenhouse gas, CO₂ traps heat in the atmosphere, significantly contributing to the greenhouse effect and subsequent global warming. According to Mackay (2008), the rise in CO₂ levels is closely linked to economic and industrial activities, including energy production, transportation, and large-scale agriculture.

CO₂ emissions are typically measured in metric tons per capita, reflecting the environmental burden imposed by individuals within a given economy. The Kyoto Protocol identifies CO₂ alongside other GHGs such as methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons, and sulfur hexafluoride as major contributors to climate change (Brander, 2012). However, CO₂ is the most abundant anthropogenic GHG, and thus often serves as a proxy for overall environmental degradation in empirical studies. The concept of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e) has been developed to standardize the warming potential of various GHGs, enabling more accurate comparisons across emission sources and countries (Brander, 2012).

Ecological Footprint

While CO₂ emissions provide a partial picture of environmental impact, the ecological footprint offers a more holistic measure. It quantifies the biologically productive area required to produce the resources consumed and absorb the waste generated by a population, given prevailing technology and resource management practices (Jović et al., 2018). The ecological footprint includes components such as cropland, forest area, fishing grounds, and carbon sequestration capacity, and is expressed in global hectares (GHA) per person (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019).

According to Al-Mulali and Sheau-Ting (2014), the ecological footprint accounts for environmental pressures beyond emissions by integrating all human demands on the biosphere, including land use, food production, and urban infrastructure. This makes it a more comprehensive indicator of environmental sustainability, especially in developing regions where resource extraction and land conversion may not be fully captured by emission data alone (Uddin et al., 2017; Charfeddine & Mrabet, 2017; Aydin et al., 2019). The ecological footprint thus serves as a reliable metric for comparing environmental impacts across time and space, enhancing the robustness of empirical analyses.

2.3 Financial Sector Development: Conceptual Framework and Indicators

Financial sector development refers to the growth, diversification, and efficiency of financial institutions, markets, and instruments that mobilize savings, facilitate investment, and manage risk within an economy (World Bank, 2016). A well-developed financial system contributes to economic growth by allocating capital efficiently and fostering innovation (Levine, 2004). It also has potential implications for environmental quality, as it can either finance environmentally harmful activities or support the transition to a green economy (Shahbaz et al., 2016; Baloch et al., 2018).

Financial development is generally assessed using both banking sector and capital market indicators. While previous studies have focused extensively on banking indicators such as credit to the private sector and liquid liabilities (Beck & Levine, 2004), this study emphasizes capital market indicators, specifically market capitalization and stock market turnover ratio, which are increasingly relevant in Sub-Saharan African economies.

Market Capitalization to GDP

Market capitalization, defined as the total value of listed shares on a country's stock exchange, relative to GDP, is a standard indicator of the size and maturity of the equity market (N'zue, 2006). A higher market capitalization ratio implies a larger stock market with enhanced capacity to raise capital for investment. Market capitalization reflects investor confidence and corporate valuation, and it is a key variable in determining how effectively a capital market can channel funds toward productive and environmentally sustainable ventures (Omodero, 2020).

As noted by Okikii and Nzomoi (2013), a robust equity market supports corporate growth and economic diversification, which may in turn influence environmental outcomes. For example, capital raised through equity markets can be directed toward clean energy technologies, sustainable infrastructure, and green manufacturing practices. Conversely, poorly regulated capital markets may fund environmentally harmful activities, exacerbating degradation.

Stock Market Turnover Ratio

The stock market turnover ratio, calculated as the value of shares traded relative to total market capitalization, serves as a proxy for market liquidity and efficiency (Adegbite, 2008). A high turnover ratio indicates an active market with greater investor participation and lower transaction costs. Efficient capital markets are more responsive to environmental risks and opportunities, enabling the integration of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors into investment decisions (World Bank, 2016).

From an environmental standpoint, a dynamic stock market can encourage transparency and corporate accountability, particularly when green investment products are introduced. It also facilitates the reallocation of capital away from polluting industries toward environmentally sustainable sectors.

2.4 Theoretical Perspectives

Several theories from the extant literature provide useful lenses for interpreting the dynamics between financial development particularly capital market indicators such as market capitalization and stock market turnover and environmental quality in Sub-Saharan African

countries. These include the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis, Ecological Modernization Theory, and Environmental Transition Theory.

Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Hypothesis

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis posits an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation. This implies that in the early stages of economic and financial development, environmental degradation tends to increase due to industrial expansion, energy consumption, and weak regulatory enforcement. However, after reaching a certain threshold of income or development, environmental quality begins to improve as societies invest in cleaner technologies, implement stricter environmental regulations, and shift toward service-based economies (Grossman & Krueger, 1995; Panayotou, 1995).

In relation to financial sector development, the EKC hypothesis suggests that increased financial activities, especially through capital markets, may initially contribute to environmental degradation by facilitating industrial expansion and energy-intensive investments. However, as financial systems mature and incorporate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards, they can support investments in sustainable infrastructure and renewable energy projects (Shahbaz et al., 2016). This transformation aligns with the later stage of the EKC, where environmental indicators begin to improve as a result of economic and technological advancement.

In the context of Sub-Saharan Africa, this hypothesis is particularly relevant. Countries in the region are at varying stages of financial and economic development, and empirical studies have shown mixed results regarding the existence of the EKC. For instance, studies by Narayan and Narayan (2010), Kwakwa and Adu (2016), and Dasuki and Olubusoye (2020) found both supporting and refuting evidence of the EKC in different African countries. This variability underscores the importance of country-specific analysis and the role of financial structure in influencing environmental outcomes.

Ecological Modernization Theory

Ecological Modernization Theory (EMT) argues that environmental protection and economic development are not necessarily incompatible. Rather than being an obstacle to growth, environmental sustainability can be achieved through technological innovation, institutional reforms, and market-based solutions (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019). According to this theory, advanced financial systems, including well-functioning capital markets, can play a critical role in fostering ecological modernization by funding green innovations and facilitating the diffusion of environmentally friendly technologies.

This theory is particularly pertinent when examining the role of stock markets. Financial instruments such as green bonds, environmental risk-adjusted investment portfolios, and socially responsible investment funds are increasingly traded on stock markets in developed economies. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the development of capital markets provides an opportunity to integrate environmental considerations into investment decision-making, thus supporting the principles of ecological modernization. However, the effectiveness of this mechanism depends heavily on institutional quality, market regulation, and investor awareness.

Environmental Transition Theory

Environmental Transition Theory complements the EKC and EMT by focusing on how societies change their environmental priorities over time as they progress economically. The theory posits that in the early phases of industrialization, economic and infrastructure development takes precedence, often at the cost of environmental degradation. However, as economies grow wealthier and more urbanized, environmental awareness increases, leading to stronger environmental governance and a transition toward sustainable practices (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019).

In relation to financial sector development, this theory suggests that the expansion of stock markets may initially support industries that contribute to environmental degradation. Yet, as institutional frameworks evolve and the financial sector becomes more sophisticated, capital markets can become effective tools for channelling investments into environmentally sustainable sectors. This transition is observable in developed markets but remains underexplored in SSA, where capital markets are still emerging and may not yet exert strong environmental oversight.

2.5 Empirical Evidence on Financial Development and Environmental Degradation

Evidence from Global and Developed Economies

Joe-Ming, Ku-Hsieh, and Chin-Ho (2015) analyzed 25 OECD countries and found that financial development exerted a statistically significant negative effect on CO₂ emissions in several nations, implying that advanced financial systems could facilitate environmentally sustainable investment decisions. In particular, financial development in Austria, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, and the United States was associated with reductions in emissions. Their study employed Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) and revealed that mature financial systems may channel resources into cleaner production technologies and efficient energy systems.

In a related study, Shahbaz, Nasir, and Roubaud (2018) examined the determinants of carbon emissions in France over the period 1955–2016. Their findings support the hypothesis that financial development enhances environmental quality by facilitating investment in energy research and innovation. The study revealed that financial sector expansion was inversely related to CO₂ emissions, whereas foreign direct investment (FDI) contributed positively to environmental degradation. These results corroborate the pollution haven hypothesis and underscore the importance of regulatory oversight in aligning financial flows with environmental goals.

Majeed and Mazhar (2019) conducted a large-scale panel study involving 131 countries and used ecological footprint rather than CO₂ emissions alone as a more comprehensive measure of environmental degradation. Their results demonstrated that all financial development indicators, including domestic credit to the private sector, significantly improved environmental quality by lowering the ecological footprint. Notably, domestic lending to the private sector had the most pronounced effect. This study underscores the importance of using broader environmental indicators, as ecological footprint captures a wider spectrum of human impacts on natural ecosystems, including carbon emissions, cropland use, fishing grounds, and built-up land.

Contrary to the above findings, some studies have reported that financial development may exacerbate environmental degradation. Shahbaz, Haouas, Sohag, and Ozturk (2020), analysing quarterly data from the UAE between 1975 and 2014, found that financial sector expansion was associated with rising CO₂ emissions. The study used the Toda-Yamamoto

causality test and discovered that increased access to financial services encouraged higher energy consumption, which ultimately degraded environmental quality. Similarly, Shahbaz, Destek, Dong, and Jiao (2021) explored the time-varying effects of financial development on CO₂ emissions in G-7 countries using data from 1870 to 2014. The results showed that the relationship followed non-linear patterns such as M-shaped or inverted N-shaped forms, depending on the country. These findings imply that the environmental implications of financial development are not constant but rather evolve with institutional maturity, regulatory enforcement, and the macroeconomic environment.

Habiba and Xinbang (2022) took a more nuanced approach by disaggregating financial development into financial institutions and financial markets. Using a two-step system GMM and data from developed and emerging economies between 2000 and 2018, they found that market-based financial development (e.g., stock market depth and efficiency) led to reductions in CO₂ emissions in both groups of countries. However, financial institution development produced divergent effects: it improved environmental quality in developed countries but worsened it in emerging ones. This divergence is potentially attributable to differences in institutional capacity, regulatory enforcement, and technological infrastructure.

These contrasting outcomes highlight the complexity of the relationship between financial development and environmental quality. In developed economies, where financial institutions and markets are more transparent, mature, and regulated, financial development may foster green innovation and environmental sustainability. However, in less developed financial environments, capital may be channelled toward energy-intensive and polluting industries due to weak environmental governance.

Evidence from Developing Economies and Sub-Saharan Africa

The empirical literature focusing on developing countries and Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) presents similarly varied findings, shaped by institutional quality, financial infrastructure, and environmental policy enforcement.

In the context of ASEAN-5 countries, Hamdan, Ab-Rahim, and Fah (2018) examined the interplay between CO₂ emissions, private domestic credit, and market capitalization from 2000 to 2014. Using Vector Error Correction Models (VECM) and Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS), they reported a bidirectional causal relationship between market capitalization and CO₂ emissions. This result suggests that financial markets not only influence environmental quality but are also affected by environmental conditions. For example, environmental risk can impact investor confidence and stock market performance.

Lestari, Effendi, and Priyono (2020) investigated the impact of both banking and capital market development on CO₂ emissions in Asian emerging economies between 1980 and 2018. Their findings indicated that financial development from the banking sector increased environmental degradation, while capital market indicators such as market capitalization showed no significant long-term impact. This result underscores the differing roles of financial sub-sectors in shaping environmental outcomes and aligns with the notion that capital markets might be more effective in promoting environmental sustainability through diversified investment portfolios and greater regulatory scrutiny.

In the African context, Mesagan and Nwanchukwu (2018) examined Nigeria's financial system and its influence on environmental quality using data from 1981 to 2016. They found that financial development, along with energy consumption and trade openness, significantly influenced environmental degradation. The results highlighted that while credit expansion

could support clean investments, it could also finance polluting industrial activities in the absence of green finance policies. Similarly, Musa, Chindo, and Maijama'a (2021) analyzed the effect of financial development and income level on CO₂ emissions in Nigeria using ARDL models. Their findings indicated a statistically significant negative relationship between financial development and CO₂ emissions in both the long and short term. This suggests that, when properly regulated, financial development can be a lever for environmental improvement through support for energy-efficient technologies and cleaner production.

Other relevant African studies include Longe et al. (2020), who found that financial development had contrasting effects on carbon emissions in Nigeria, depending on the time horizon. While financial development positively impacted emissions in the short run due to increased consumption and industrialization, it had a negative long-term effect as investments in green infrastructure matured.

Kwakwa, Alhassan, and Aboagye (2018) further explored the dual impact of financial development and natural resource extraction on CO₂ emissions in Tunisia. The study found that the EKC hypothesis holds depending on the source of CO₂ emissions, with financial development reducing emissions from manufacturing but increasing emissions from fossil fuel consumption.

Tahir et al. (2021) and Khuky (2021) also provided evidence from South Asia and Bangladesh, respectively, supporting the view that financial development can either improve or worsen environmental quality depending on accompanying institutional frameworks and the direction of capital flows.

In sum, empirical evidence from SSA and other developing regions demonstrates that the relationship between financial sector development and environmental degradation is multifaceted and context-specific. Key financial indicators such as market capitalization and stock market turnover may either mitigate or exacerbate environmental harm depending on the degree of market maturity, regulatory oversight, and the orientation of capital toward green or brown sectors. This study contributes to the growing body of literature by focusing on how these specific capital market indicators influence environmental outcomes in selected SSA countries. By incorporating both carbon dioxide emissions and ecological footprint as environmental indicators, it also seeks to offer a more holistic assessment of environmental degradation.

3. Methodology

This study adopts a longitudinal panel data research design to investigate the relationship between financial sector development and environmental degradation in selected Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. A panel approach enables the exploration of both temporal and cross-sectional variations, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of the financial-environment nexus. The design supports causal inference by accounting for both within-country and between-country heterogeneity over the period 1993 to 2021 (Habiba & Xinbang, 2022; Majeed & Mazhar, 2019).

The study focuses on seven SSA countries: Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Kenya, Mauritius, Namibia, Nigeria, and South Africa. These countries were selected using a purposive sampling strategy based on three criteria: (i) availability of consistent data from 1995 to 2023; (ii) relatively advanced capital markets within the SSA region; and (iii) geographical representation across West, East, and Southern Africa.

Data for financial development and environmental degradation variables were sourced from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) and the Global Footprint Network (2022). These databases are recognized for their credibility and consistency in macroeconomic and environmental data reporting (Shahbaz et al., 2020; Lestari et al., 2020).

3.1 Model Specification

The ARDL econometric model employed in this study assesses the impact of financial sector development on environmental degradation in selected Sub-Saharan African countries, using two key environmental indicators: carbon dioxide emissions per capita (CO₂) and ecological footprint per capita (EFP). Financial development is proxied by market capitalization to GDP (MKC), which reflects the size and depth of capital markets, and stock market turnover ratio (SMT), which indicates market liquidity and trading activity. To control for other environmental drivers, the model includes energy consumption per capita (ENC), urbanization (URB), foreign direct investment (FDI), and secondary school enrolment (SER) as a measure of human capital. All variables are transformed into their natural logarithmic forms to ensure interpretability in elasticity terms and to mitigate potential heteroskedasticity in the panel dataset.

Model 1: ARDL Model for Financial Development and Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln CO_{2it} = & \alpha_0 + \phi_1 \ln CO_{2it-1} + \phi_2 \ln MKC_{it-1} + \phi_3 \ln SMT_{it-1} + \phi_4 \ln ENC_{it-1} + \phi_5 \ln URB_{it-1} \\ & + \phi_6 \ln FDI_{it-1} + \phi_7 \ln SER_{it-1} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^p \delta_1^j \Delta \ln CO_{2it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \delta_2^j \Delta \ln MKC_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^r \delta_3^j \Delta \ln SMT_{it-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^s \delta_4^j \Delta \ln ENC_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^u \delta_5^j \Delta \ln URB_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^v \delta_6^j \Delta \ln FDI_{it-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^w \delta_7^j \Delta \ln SER_{it-j} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Model 2: ARDL Model for Financial Development and Ecological Footprint (EFP)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln EFP_{it} = & \alpha_0 + \phi_1 \ln EFP_{it-1} + \phi_2 \ln MKC_{it-1} + \phi_3 \ln SMT_{it-1} + \phi_4 \ln ENC_{it-1} + \phi_5 \ln URB_{it-1} \\ & + \phi_6 \ln FDI_{it-1} + \phi_7 \ln SER_{it-1} \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^p \delta_1^j \Delta \ln EFP_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \delta_2^j \Delta \ln MKC_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^r \delta_3^j \Delta \ln SMT_{it-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^s \delta_4^j \Delta \ln ENC_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^u \delta_5^j \Delta \ln URB_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^v \delta_6^j \Delta \ln FDI_{it-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^w \delta_7^j \Delta \ln SER_{it-j} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Where:

- Δ : First difference operator
- $\ln CO_{2it}$: Natural log of carbon dioxide emissions per capita for country iii in year ttt
- $\ln EFP_{it}$: Natural log of ecological footprint per capita

- $\ln MKC_{it}$: Natural log of market capitalization to GDP (financial market depth)
- $\ln SMT_{it}$: Natural log of stock market turnover ratio (financial market liquidity)
- $\ln ENC_{it}$: Natural log of energy consumption per capita
- $\ln URB_{it}$: Natural log of urban population share
- $\ln FDI_{it}$: Natural log of foreign direct investment to GDP
- $\ln SER_{it}$: Natural log of secondary school enrolment rate
- ε_{it} : Error term capturing shocks or omitted variables
- ϕ_k : Long-run parameters
- δ_k^j : Short-run dynamic coefficients
- p, q, r, s, u, v, w : Optimal lag lengths determined by information criteria (e.g., AIC, BIC)

These ARDL models are suitable for mixed orders of integration (i.e., I (0) and I (1)) and provide flexibility in estimating both short-run and long-run effects, while controlling for country-specific heterogeneity and dynamics over time.

3.2 Variable Measurements and Expectations

Variable	Proxy	Expected Sign	Justification
CO₂	Carbon emissions (metric tons per capita)	-/+	Environmental degradation indicator (Alabi et al., 2021)
EFP	Ecological footprint (gha per capita)	-/+	Broader measure of environmental pressure (Khuky, 2021)
MKC	Market capitalization to GDP (%)	-/+	May promote green finance or support polluting sectors (Aljadani, A. (2022)
SMT	Stock market turnover ratio (%)	-/+	Reflects capital market activity and potential pollution financing (Lestari et al., 2020)
ENC	Energy use per capita	+	Higher energy use linked to more emissions (Longe et al., 2020)
URB	Urban population (% total)	+	Urban growth typically increases pollution (Kwakwa & Alhassan, 2020)
FDI	Net inflows (% of GDP)	+	Can contribute to industrial pollution (Ibrahim, M. & Vo, X. V. 2021).
SER	Secondary school enrolment rate (%)	-	Human capital improves environmental awareness (Kwakwa & Alhassan, 2020)

Author's Compilation (2025)

3.3 Estimation Techniques

The study employs a panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, estimated using both the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) and Mean Group (MG) estimators. The PMG estimator allows for heterogeneity in short-run coefficients while imposing homogeneity in

long-run parameters across countries. The MG estimator, by contrast, allows for full heterogeneity across all dimensions (Pesaran et al., 1999).

To validate the suitability of the ARDL framework, the following diagnostics are conducted:

- Panel Unit Root Tests: Using the Im, Pesaran and Shin (2003) approach to test the stationarity properties of the variables.
- Panel Cointegration Tests: Using Pedroni (1999, 2001) residual-based tests to confirm the existence of long-run equilibrium relationships among variables.

Granger Causality Analysis

To investigate the directional relationship between financial development and environmental degradation, the study applies a panel Granger causality test. The purpose is to determine whether capital market indicators (MKC and SMT) Granger-cause changes in environmental outcomes (CO₂ and EFP) or vice versa. The multivariate specification is as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m \alpha_k Y_{it-k} + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j X_{it-j} + \mu_{it}$$

$$X_{it} = \gamma_0 + \sum_{k=1}^m \gamma_k X_{it-k} + \sum_{j=1}^n \delta_j Y_{it-j} + \eta_{it}$$

Where:

- Y_{it} = CO₂ or EFP,
- X_{it} = MKC or SMT,
- μ_{it}, η_{it} = error terms.

Granger causality is inferred when the lagged values of the independent variable significantly explain variation in the dependent variable beyond its own lags.

4. Results and Discussions

This section presents the empirical results of the study using several statistical tools, including trend analysis, descriptive statistics, unit root tests, correlation analysis, cointegration tests, the ARDL model for long- and short-run estimates, and Granger causality tests.

Figure 1a Trends in CO₂ Emissions and Ecological Footprint

Source: Author's computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

Figure 1b Trends in Ecological Footprint

Source: Author's computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

Figure 1 depicts a clear and steady increase in total CO₂ emissions across the Sub-Saharan African countries examined in the study, reflecting a growing, though still relatively modest, contribution to global environmental degradation compared to more industrialized nations. For instance, Côte d'Ivoire's emissions rose from approximately 4 million tonnes in 1995 to over 10 million tonnes by 2023, while Nigeria experienced a sharper rise, with emissions increasing from 40 million to 120 million tonnes during the same period. In Figure 2, the ecological footprint per capita is shown separately for cropland (EFPC) and built-up land (EFPI), revealing notable inter-country variation. EFPC is most significant in Côte d'Ivoire, Namibia, and South Africa, whereas EFPI is more pronounced in Ghana, Nigeria, and Mauritius. With the exception of Mauritius—where a downward trend is observed—most countries display either stable or rising ecological footprints, pointing to a progressive escalation in environmental stress across the region.

Figure 2: Trends in Capital Market Development Variables

Source: Author's computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

Figure 2 presents trends in capital market development, measured by stock market capitalization-to-GDP and stock turnover ratios. The data reveal unstable annual movements across countries, with only South Africa showing a sustained upward trend in both indicators. In contrast, most countries exhibit flat trajectories, and Ghana has experienced a decline in market capitalization since 2015. Overall, the evidence suggests limited progress in capital market development across Sub-Saharan Africa, with only marginal and short-lived improvements observed over time.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Panel Data

Variable	Mean	Max.	Min.	Std. Dev.	Skew.	Kurt.	J-B	Prob.
GCO2	4.51	99.11	-26.23	13.39	2.12	14.71	1402.96	0.00
EFPC	0.73	1.24	0.18	0.25	-0.28	2.68	3.83	0.15
EFPI	2.20	16.08	0.11	4.00	2.35	7.05	348.42	0.00
MKT	7.92	124.37	0.03	20.48	3.20	13.14	1300.03	0.00
SMT	8.16	80.38	0.35	10.03	2.99	15.96	1842.94	0.00
FDI	2.23	10.66	-1.42	2.25	1.58	5.19	133.22	0.00
URB	42.46	67.85	17.04	11.83	-0.19	2.64	2.47	0.29
SER	2.05	4.01	1.24	0.42	0.65	5.84	88.52	0.00
GENC	2.83	187.03	-31.43	18.01	6.48	62.24	33248.26	0.00

Source: Author's computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the panel data variables, revealing substantial variability and distributional characteristics relevant for the analysis. The mean growth in CO₂ emissions (GCO2) is 4.51%, with a high standard deviation of 13.39, indicating significant fluctuations across countries and time. Its pronounced positive skewness (2.12) and high kurtosis (14.71), confirmed by a significant Jarque-Bera (J-B) test ($p = 0.00$),

suggest a non-normal distribution driven by outliers or extreme values. Similarly, both market capitalization (MKT) and stock market turnover (SMT) exhibit high skewness (3.20 and 2.99) and leptokurtic distributions, reflecting large disparities in capital market development, particularly between South Africa and other countries. The ecological footprint indicators—EFPC and EFPI—show lower mean values, with EFPC being relatively normally distributed (J-B $p = 0.15$), while EFPI is highly skewed and leptokurtic, indicating uneven environmental stress. Other variables such as foreign direct investment (FDI) and school enrolment (SER) also show significant deviations from normality, while urbanization (URB) is the only variable that appears normally distributed ($p = 0.29$).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Individual Countries

COUNTRY	GCO2	EFPC	EFPI	MKT	SMT
Côte d'Ivoire	4.32	0.79	0.56	0.38	2.55
Ghana	6.39	0.84	1.04	0.34	3.68
Kenya	4.72	0.62	0.63	1.17	4.02
Mauritius	3.79	1.06	11.66	2.51	5.33
Namibia	5.30	0.28	0.13	0.35	9.66
Nigeria	5.85	0.64	0.75	1.01	7.48
South Africa	1.21	0.85	0.70	48.21	23.30

Source: Author's computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

Table 2 provides country-level descriptive statistics that highlight significant disparities in environmental and financial indicators among the selected Sub-Saharan African economies. In terms of CO₂ emissions growth (GCO2), Ghana (6.39%) and Nigeria (5.85%) report the highest average values, indicating more intense environmental pressure, while South Africa has the lowest (1.21%), possibly reflecting more advanced mitigation policies. The ecological footprint per capita (EFPC) is highest in Mauritius (1.06), followed by Ghana and South Africa, while Namibia records the lowest (0.28), suggesting limited resource consumption relative to others. A stark contrast is evident in the ecological footprint index (EFPI), where Mauritius stands out with a significantly higher value (11.66), pointing to elevated environmental stress. In terms of capital market development, South Africa dominates both in market capitalization (48.21% of GDP) and stock market turnover (23.30%), reflecting a more mature financial system. Other countries, such as Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and Namibia, exhibit minimal market activity, underscoring the underdevelopment of capital markets in much of the region.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variable	CO2	EFPC	EFPI	MKT	SMT	FDI	ENC	URB	SER
CO2	1								
EFPC	0.21 (0.00)	1							
EFPI	-0.19 (0.00)	0.61 (0.00)	1						

MKT	0.86 (0.00)	0.27 (0.00)	-0.10 (0.14)	1					
SMT	0.68 (0.00)	0.05 (0.42)	-0.11 (0.11)	0.72 (0.00)	1				
FDI	-0.16 (0.02)	-0.11 (0.12)	-0.07 (0.30)	-0.08 (0.26)	0.12 (0.06)	1			
ENC	0.82 (0.00)	0.19 (0.00)	0.09 (0.20)	0.62 (0.00)	0.62 (0.00)	0.00 (0.94)	1		
URB	0.63 (0.00)	0.41 (0.00)	0.02 (0.73)	0.57 (0.00)	0.45 (0.00)	0.13 (0.06)	0.61 (0.00)	1	
SER	0.35 (0.00)	0.27 (0.00)	0.27 (0.00)	0.51 (0.00)	0.37 (0.00)	0.24 (0.00)	0.54 (0.00)	0.37 (0.00)	1

Source: Author’s computation (2025) with the aid of E-view 9.0 econometric software

The correlation matrix in Table 3 reveals several statistically significant relationships among the variables, highlighting key dynamics between financial development and environmental degradation. CO₂ emissions show a strong positive correlation with market capitalization (MKT) ($r = 0.86$, $p < 0.01$), stock market turnover (SMT) ($r = 0.68$), and energy consumption (ENC) ($r = 0.82$), suggesting that financial market activity and energy use are major contributors to emissions in the region. A moderate positive correlation also exists between CO₂ and urbanization (URB) ($r = 0.63$), supporting the hypothesis that expanding urban infrastructure contributes to environmental stress. In contrast, ecological footprint index (EFPI) is negatively correlated with CO₂ ($r = -0.19$), but strongly positively associated with ecological footprint per capita (EFPC) ($r = 0.61$), indicating that the two footprint measures capture different dimensions of environmental pressure. Interestingly, foreign direct investment (FDI) shows weak and mostly negative correlations with environmental indicators, reflecting a possibly limited or context-dependent environmental impact of capital inflows. Moreover, school enrolment (SER) is positively correlated with most financial and environmental indicators, suggesting a linkage between human capital development and broader economic and environmental dynamics.

Table 4a: Panel Data Unit Root Tests Results in Levels

Variables	<i>Common unit process</i>	<i>individual unit root process</i>		
	LLC	IPS	ADF	PP-Fisher
LCO2	-2.63**	0.37	10.31	9.72
EFPC	0.21	-0.52	17.31	33.82*
EFPI	2.06**	-0.60	28.41*	43.53*
MKT	-3.26**	-2.87*	31.65*	38.62*
SMT	-4.27**	-4.35**	46.97**	53.42**
ENC	-0.93	1.39	8.11	6.53
FDI	-2.25**	-3.56**	36.96**	52.69**
URB	0.07	3.60	4.61	27.41
SER	-1.80	5.72	4.87	0.64

Source: Estimated by the Author. Note: ** and * indicate significant at 1% and 5 % levels respectively; IPS = Im, Pesaran & Shin; LLC = Levin, Lin & Chu

Table 4b: Panel Data Unit Root Tests Results in First Differences

Variables	<i>Common unit process</i>	<i>individual unit root process</i>		
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	LLC	IPS	ADF	PP-Fisher
LCO2	-7.60**	-8.61**	93.85**	176.2**
EFPC	-10.51**	-12.77**	132.8**	186.4**
EFPI	-7.13**	-13.28**	138.8**	209.4**
MKT	-10.51**	-11.09**	123.6**	188.3**
SMT	-12.06**	-11.49**	128.5**	189.4**
ENC	-6.67**	-6.79*	72.29**	165.7**
FDI	-7.49**	-10.75**	120.0**	189.4**
SER	4.03*	1.63	7.618	45.62**
URB	3.86*	3.56*	5.673	6.83

Source: Estimated by the Author. *Note:* ** and * indicate significant at 1% and 5 % levels respectively; IPS = Im, Pesaran & Shin; LLC = Levin, Lin & Chu

The unit root test results in Tables 4a and 4b assess the stationarity properties of the panel data variables and reveal that most variables are non-stationary at levels but become stationary after first differencing, indicating that they are integrated of order one, I(1). At levels (Table 4a), only market capitalization (MKT), stock market turnover (SMT), and foreign direct investment (FDI) consistently reject the null hypothesis of a unit root across both the common (LLC) and individual (IPS, ADF, PP-Fisher) unit root tests at 1% or 5% significance levels. CO₂ emissions (LCO2) and ecological footprint index (EFPI) show mixed evidence of stationarity, while variables like urbanization (URB), school enrolment (SER), and energy consumption (ENC) are clearly non-stationary. In contrast, first difference results (Table 4b) demonstrate that nearly all variables—including environmental indicators, financial development proxies, and control variables—are stationary across all test specifications, confirming their I(1) nature. This validates the use of panel cointegration techniques, such as the P-ARDL model, which accommodate mixed orders of integration and allow for both short-run and long-run dynamics in the analysis.

Table 5: Cross-section Dependence Test Results

Equation series tested	Pesaran CD	P-value	Abs corr
CO ₂	0.635	0.516	0.144
EFC	1.123	0.239	0.195
EFPI	-0.692	0.488	0.170

Source: Author's computations (2025)

Table 5 presents the results of the Pesaran Cross-Section Dependence (CD) tests for the key environmental indicators—CO₂ emissions (CO₂), ecological footprint per capita (EFC), and ecological footprint index (EFPI). The p-values for all three series are above the conventional significance threshold (CO₂: p = 0.516; EFC: p = 0.239; EFPI: p = 0.488), indicating that the null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence cannot be rejected. This suggests that environmental degradation patterns in the sampled Sub-Saharan African countries are not significantly influenced by common shocks or contemporaneous spillovers across countries.

Table 6: Results of Bounds Test of Cointegration

Country	F-statistic	I(0)	I(1)
Côte d'Ivoire	54.86	2.04	2.08

Ghana	3.72	2.04	2.08
Kenya	82.93	2.04	2.08
Mauritius	11.34	2.04	2.08
Namibia	13.44	2.04	2.08
Nigeria	5.12	2.04	2.08
South Africa	2.12	2.04	2.08

Source: Author's computation (2025)

Table 6 presents the results of the bounds test for cointegration across the selected Sub-Saharan African countries. The F-statistics for Côte d'Ivoire (54.86), Kenya (82.93), Mauritius (11.34), Namibia (13.44), and Nigeria (5.12) all exceed the upper critical bound value of 2.08 at the 5% significance level, indicating strong evidence of a long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables in these countries. Ghana, with an F-statistic of 3.72, also surpasses the upper bound, albeit marginally, suggesting a weaker but valid cointegration. South Africa, however, shows an F-statistic (2.12) that is only slightly above the lower bound and falls within the inconclusive region, implying no definitive evidence of a long-run relationship. Overall, the results confirm the presence of stable long-run interactions between financial development and environmental degradation in most of the countries studied.

Table 4.7: Short Run PMG Estimates- Regression Results for the Effects of Financial Development (Capital Market Development) on Environmental Degradation

<i>Variable</i>	<i>LCO2</i>			<i>EFPC</i>			<i>EFPI</i>		
	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.
<i>Constant</i>	3.172	2.934	0.00	0.030	0.140	0.89	0.510	0.423	0.67
ΔMKT	0.066	1.656	0.10	-0.015	-1.334	0.19	-0.065	-1.454	0.15
ΔMKT_{t-1}	0.097	1.349	0.18	-0.005	-1.058	0.29	-0.117	-1.160	0.25
ΔSMT	-0.009	-1.239	0.22	0.004	1.048	0.30	0.043	0.878	0.38
ΔSMT_{t-1}	-0.016	-2.085	0.04	0.006	1.454	0.15	0.079	1.017	0.31
$\Delta LENC$	0.330	1.236	0.22	-0.270	-1.156	0.25	-0.624	-1.213	0.23
$\Delta LENC_{t-1}$	0.277	1.491	0.14	-0.279	-1.068	0.29	0.152	0.164	0.87
ΔURB	3.655	1.501	0.14	0.678	1.241	0.22	-6.678	-1.009	0.32
ΔURB_{t-1}	-3.518	-1.450	0.15	-1.508	-2.048	0.04	-0.769	-0.729	0.47
ΔFDI	0.007	0.549	0.58	-0.011	-1.479	0.14	-0.039	-1.376	0.17
ΔFDI_{t-1}	0.000	0.020	0.98	-0.004	-0.925	0.36	0.027	0.774	0.44
ΔSER	3.688	1.238	0.22	3.774	0.998	0.32	27.358	1.100	0.27
ΔSER_{t-1}	4.828	0.990	0.33	-1.148	-0.299	0.77	-48.494	-1.109	0.27
ECM_{t-1}	-0.511	-2.882	0.01	-0.659	-4.042	0.00	-0.010	-0.153	0.88
<i>S.E. of reg.</i>	0.088			0.000			-0.047		
<i>Mean dep. Var.</i>	0.038			0.049			0.401		

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The short-run Panel Mean Group (PMG) estimates in Table 4.7 examine how capital market development, captured by market capitalization (MKT) and stock market turnover (SMT), influences environmental degradation across Sub-Saharan African countries using three indicators: CO₂ emissions (LCO₂), ecological footprint per capita (EFPC), and ecological footprint index (EFPI). In the short term, the coefficients of MKT and SMT are mostly statistically insignificant, indicating weak immediate effects of capital market activities on

environmental indicators. However, the lagged value of SMT (ΔSMT_{t-1}) shows a statistically significant negative effect on CO₂ emissions ($p = 0.04$), suggesting that stock market liquidity may contribute to emission reductions over time, possibly by facilitating delayed investments in cleaner technologies or by reallocating resources away from polluting sectors. This finding echoes the postulations of the Ecological Modernization Theory, which asserts that mature and liquid markets can eventually support environmental improvements through enhanced information flow, innovation financing, and investor pressure on corporate environmental performance (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019). Conversely, the absence of significant effects from current MKT or SMT values on EFPC and EFPI may reflect the underdeveloped nature of capital markets in most SSA countries, where green investment products and ESG standards remain limited or ineffective (Hamdan et al., 2018).

Additionally, the error correction terms (ECM_{t-1}) are significantly negative for both CO₂ emissions (-0.511 , $p = 0.01$) and EFPC (-0.659 , $p = 0.00$), confirming the existence of stable long-run equilibrium relationships and indicating that any deviations from long-run environmental paths are corrected over time. The absence of significance in the EFPI model suggests a weaker adjustment mechanism for broader ecological pressures. The broader implication is that while short-term capital market effects on environmental quality may be limited or lagged, structural and institutional reforms could strengthen the role of capital markets as tools for ecological sustainability. This is consistent with findings by Shahbaz et al. (2018) and Majeed and Mazhar (2019), who emphasize that the environmental impact of financial development depends on the maturity, regulatory quality, and green orientation of financial systems.

Table 4.8a: Long Run PMG Estimates

<i>Variable</i>	<i>LCO2</i>			<i>EFPC</i>			<i>EFPI</i>		
	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.	Coeff.	t-ratio	prob.
<i>MKT</i>	-0.102	-4.234	0.00	-0.006	-8.035	0.00	0.091	2.387	0.02
<i>SMT</i>	0.020	3.801	0.00	-0.009	-6.738	0.00	-0.187	-2.730	0.01
<i>LENC</i>	0.178	3.025	0.00	0.080	2.244	0.03	-4.659	-2.661	0.01
<i>URB</i>	0.076	4.063	0.00	0.028	8.209	0.00	0.142	1.595	0.11
<i>FDI</i>	0.004	0.389	0.70	0.003	2.220	0.03	-0.235	-2.759	0.01
<i>SER</i>	-0.417	-0.716	0.48	-0.687	-8.770	0.00	-10.572	-2.372	0.02

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The long-run Panel Mean Group (PMG) estimates in Table 4.8a provide insightful evidence on the differentiated impacts of capital market development—measured by market capitalization (MKT) and stock market turnover (SMT)—on environmental degradation indicators across Sub-Saharan African countries. Market capitalization exhibits a statistically significant negative relationship with CO₂ emissions (-0.102 , $p = 0.00$) and ecological footprint per capita (-0.006 , $p = 0.00$), implying that deepening capital markets may support long-term environmental sustainability, possibly by channelling investments into cleaner technologies and sustainable infrastructure, as posited by Ecological Modernization Theory (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019; Shahbaz et al., 2016). However, the positive and significant effect of MKT on the ecological footprint index (0.091 , $p = 0.02$) suggests that broader land and resource pressures may still persist despite emission reductions, reflecting incomplete transitions in some economies. In contrast, stock market turnover (SMT) positively affects

CO₂ emissions (0.020, $p = 0.00$), while reducing both EFPC and EFPI, indicating that while increased trading activity may initially stimulate environmentally intensive activities, it also promotes efficiency and liquidity that can, over time, facilitate a shift toward sustainable investments. These results align with findings from Habiba and Xinbang (2022) and Shahbaz et al. (2018), who emphasize the nuanced and bidirectional relationship between financial markets and environmental outcomes.

Table 4.8b: Individual Country Long Run Results

Variable	Cote d'Ivoire		Ghana		Kenya		Mauritius		Namibia		Nigeria		South Africa	
	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.	Coeff.	Prob.
<i>MKT</i>	-1.099	0.023	0.297	0.527	-0.203	0.009	-0.092	0.001	-0.049	0.854	-0.042	0.045	0.000	0.835
<i>SMT</i>	0.128	0.049	-0.208	0.016	0.069	0.013	0.032	0.018	0.033	0.012	0.010	0.104	0.000	0.995
<i>LENC</i>	0.798	0.323	-0.747	0.535	-3.227	0.010	0.612	0.027	-0.050	0.744	1.030	0.001	1.719	0.036
<i>FDI</i>	0.348	0.053	-0.171	0.006	0.081	0.031	0.001	0.933	-0.073	0.043	0.006	0.735	0.010	0.282
<i>URB</i>	0.335	0.258	0.850	0.001	2.143	0.016	-5.698	0.001	-0.032	0.395	-0.035	0.509	0.562	0.175
<i>SER</i>	0.717	0.937	-26.90	0.002	-15.003	0.027	-16.42	0.013	4.381	0.092	1.776	0.275	-0.071	0.565
<i>Constant</i>	16.869	0.069	1.048	0.893	17.428	0.155	341.2	0.007	17.095	0.047	16.09	0.000	-0.252	0.200

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The individual country long-run estimates in Table 4.8b underscore the heterogeneity in the relationship between capital market development and environmental degradation across Sub-Saharan African countries, reflecting the contextual nuances identified in the literature (Majeed & Mazhar, 2019; Shahbaz et al., 2016). Market capitalization (MKT) exhibits a significantly negative association with environmental degradation in Côte d'Ivoire (-1.099 , $p = 0.023$), Kenya (-0.203 , $p = 0.009$), Mauritius (-0.092 , $p = 0.001$), and Nigeria (-0.042 , $p = 0.045$), supporting the view that deeper equity markets may channel funds toward environmentally sustainable activities, consistent with the predictions of the Ecological Modernization Theory. However, Ghana and South Africa show no significant or ambiguous MKT effects, indicating that institutional capacity and sectoral credit allocation may mediate these outcomes. Stock market turnover (SMT), by contrast, displays mixed results—positively associated with environmental degradation in Côte d'Ivoire and Kenya but negatively in Ghana—suggesting that increased trading activity can either exacerbate or mitigate environmental harm depending on the direction of capital flows and governance structures (Habiba & Xinbang, 2022).

Table 4.9: Causality Test Result

Null Hypothesis:	W-Stat.	Zbar-Stat.	Prob.
MKT does not homogeneously cause LCO2	0.980	-1.332	0.183
LCO2 does not homogeneously cause MKT	3.200	1.144	0.253
SMT does not homogeneously cause LCO2	2.364	0.212	0.832
LCO2 does not homogeneously cause SMT	2.434	0.290	0.772
MKT does not homogeneously cause EFPC	4.239	2.303	0.021
EFPC does not homogeneously cause MKT	3.738	1.744	0.081
SMT does not homogeneously cause EFPC	4.715	2.172	0.042
EFPC does not homogeneously cause SMT	3.248	1.198	0.231
LCO2 does not homogeneously cause LGDPPC	3.427	1.398	0.162
LGDPPC does not homogeneously cause LCO2	6.513	4.840	0.000
EFPC does not homogeneously cause LGDPPC	2.740	0.631	0.528
LGDPPC does not homogeneously cause EFPC	8.331	6.868	0.000
EFPI does not homogeneously cause LGDPPC	3.061	0.990	0.322
LGDPPC does not homogeneously cause EFPI	12.161	11.140	0.000

Source: Author's computation (2025)

The causality test results in Table 4.9 reveal key directional relationships between capital market development and environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa, offering empirical nuance to the theoretical expectations discussed in the literature. Notably, neither market capitalization (MKT) nor stock market turnover (SMT) demonstrates a statistically significant causal impact on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (LCO₂), nor does CO₂ significantly influence these capital market variables. This lack of causality suggests that, in the short term, capital market dynamics may not directly drive emission levels—an outcome possibly attributable to the relatively nascent nature of capital markets and weak environmental-financial linkages in SSA (Lestari et al., 2020; Shahbaz et al., 2020). However, both MKT and SMT exhibit significant unidirectional causality toward ecological footprint per capita (EFPC) at the 5% level ($p = 0.021$ and $p = 0.042$ respectively), indicating that capital market activity influences broader environmental stress factors beyond emissions, such as land use and biocapacity consumption (Al-Mulali & Sheau-Ting, 2014). Furthermore, GDP per capita (LGDPPC) strongly causes all three environmental indicators (LCO₂, EFPC, EFPI), reinforcing the "scale effect" of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (Grossman & Krueger, 1995; Dasuki & Olubusoye, 2020).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study provides empirical evidence on the relationship between capital market development and environmental degradation in selected Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries using market capitalization and stock market turnover as key proxies. The results reveal mixed and indicator-sensitive effects. In the short run, capital market indicators exert largely insignificant or lagged effects on carbon emissions and ecological footprint, with only lagged stock market turnover significantly reducing CO₂ emissions. However, the long-run results suggest that deeper capital markets—specifically higher market capitalization—are significantly associated with reduced carbon emissions and per capita ecological footprint, supporting the premise of Ecological Modernization Theory. Still, the positive long-run effect of market capitalization on the ecological footprint index indicates persistent pressure on land and bio capacity resources. Country-specific estimates further highlight the heterogeneity of these effects, confirming that institutional quality, financial maturity, and regulatory frameworks shape the environmental impact of capital market development across SSA economies.

First, policymakers in SSA should prioritize reforms that enhance the environmental governance of capital markets. This includes mainstreaming Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) standards, introducing green bonds, and encouraging sustainable disclosure practices among publicly listed firms. Strengthening market transparency and regulatory oversight can help ensure that capital is directed toward environmentally sustainable sectors. Furthermore, regional financial bodies such as the African Securities Exchanges Association (ASEA) should facilitate the harmonization of green finance frameworks across member states to accelerate ecological transition through capital market instruments.

Second, governments should invest in financial market infrastructure and human capital to deepen market sophistication and liquidity. Capacity-building initiatives aimed at improving environmental risk assessment among institutional investors and regulators are critical. Parallel efforts should target expanding financial literacy and promoting public awareness of green investment opportunities. These initiatives, coupled with targeted incentives for firms adopting cleaner technologies, would not only improve environmental outcomes but also bolster investor confidence in SSA capital markets, enabling a virtuous cycle of green economic development.

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